

LASER SHOCK TEST APPLICATION FOR MECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION OF FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Laser shock technique has been already used for several applications, for example to test adhesion quality in bonded composites. The aim of this paper is to study the ability of this technique to characterise fibre/matrix adhesion in composites. Specific specimens have been made, composed of single hemp yarn impregnated with epoxy matrix. As the water sensitivity of natural fibres is a real issue, some of the samples have been immersed in water at ambient temperature with the objective to study the effect of water ageing on the interface.

After laser shocks, damage observations have been made by optical microscopy. Two kinds of damage have been observed: resin cracks, which appear for high laser intensity values and interfacial micro-damage with conical shape, which appears for low intensities. Samples have been tested at different laser intensity levels, and microscopic observations allow the determination of thresholds for both types of damage. These preliminary results demonstrate the ability of the laser shock test to study and quantify the mechanical quality of yarn/matrix interface.

1 INTRODUCTION

Eco-composites are nowadays increasingly used for their numerous advantages [1]. However, one of the main problems when considering these materials is the weak fibre/matrix adhesion between the hydrophilic reinforcement and the hydrophobic matrix. Indeed, the best performance strength of a composite material is achieved when the ability to transfer stress across the fibre-matrix interface is high, i.e. when adhesion is the best. Therefore, the characterisation of fibre/matrix adhesion is an essential point for composite materials optimisation. Different types of tests are classically available, such as the push-out and pull-out tests, the fragmentation test or the microbond test. In literature, there are plenty of papers dealing with these tests on synthetic fibres [2–5].

Concerning natural fibre composites, some papers on interfacial properties measurements have been published, but many fewer than in case of synthetic fibres [6–10]. Few papers deal with interfacial tests with a single yarn, for example on a hemp yarn with epoxy matrix [11] or on a hemp yarn with soy resin [12].

In this paper, the objective is to use another type of interfacial adhesion test, based on the laser shock wave method. This technique, was first developed by Vossen and Gupta [13,14]. It can create a short but intense internal loading into the shock sample. Thanks to the wave transmission/reflection through the irradiated material, localised tension in the loading direction can be generated. These stresses could open or not the interface to test. The laser shock adhesion test (LASAT) technique was developed for many applications, especially for metal assemblies or metal coatings, for which it is now well understood [15]. Recently, this technique has also been successfully used and optimised to test different bonding strengths of composite assemblies [16] and to test inter-ply adhesion in hybrid composites [17].

Following this principle, the present paper aims to investigate the possibility of using the laser shock adhesion test to study the adhesion between a single hemp yarn and an epoxy matrix. Moreover, as the moisture influence is a crucial problem in such composites, some samples have been tested after water sorption. After the shocks, all samples were recovered and damage micromechanisms have been

analysed by microscopic observations. This study has been performed on two types of epoxy resins: a synthetic one and a partially bio-based one [18]. This paper presents results obtained with the fully synthetic epoxy resin.

The test campaign has been conducted using a laser source available in the Pprime Institute (France). Several samples have been tested in each configuration, with different laser shock intensities, in order to determine corresponding damage threshold of the fibre/matrix interface.

2 SHOCK WAVE TECHNIQUE

The principle of shock generation by use of laser source is described in Fig. 1. The laser is focused on the specimen surface, where an aluminium coating forces the laser/matter interaction to be produced on the sample surface, thus enabling a shock generation inside the target. This is necessary because epoxy resin is about 70% transparent to the 1053 nm wavelength laser source. When the laser beam is directed and focused onto the surface of the sample, such amount of energy causes the sublimation of the aluminium coating, and the plasma created, pushed by a confinement mater, induces a reaction force in the form of a pressure shock wave that is propagated through the material (Fig. 1a), and the propagation of shock waves through the specimen thickness can first be simply described by a schematic space/time diagram (Fig. 1b) [17, 18]. When the shock wave reaches the back face of the material and meets the air, a release wave is generated in the opposite direction. This release wave comes across another release wave generated in the front face of the material at the end of the laser pulse; at this point the material is subjected to a high load state which can damage the material if the local damage threshold is exceeded. This approach is quite simple, and relies on a one dimension description.

Figure 1: a) Sketch of the laser/matter interaction used to study the laser-induced shock wave propagation into a target of homogeneous material, b) Time-Position diagram representing the one-dimensional propagation of shock and release waves into a target in the case of homogeneous material.

Figure 2: a) PPrime-ENSMA's laser source, b) water as confining medium on sample surface.

The Nd-Yag laser source available at Pprime Institute (Fig. 2a) has the following characteristics: a wavelength of 1053 nm, a pulse-width about 25 ns and a maximal energy level of 20 J. This source is particularly interesting for research purposes given the fact that it offers a significant flexibility in those aspects concerning energy and laser pulse duration. A charge of 5 GW/cm² can be obtained for a 4 mm diameter target. The energy level can be tuned by using optical densities on the beam path. Water confining was used to enhance the plasma expansion effect (Fig. 2b). It helps increasing the pressure level, and it also increases the duration of the resulting pressure loading.

3 MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The studied composite material is made of a single hemp yarn impregnated with epoxy resin.

The yarn is composed of hemp fibres which have an average diameter of $13 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$ [19]. Those yarns are produced with twist level of 324 tpm (yarn surface twist angle of 11°) and a linear density of 83tex. Besides the irregular cross-section, the hemp yarns have an apparent diameter of about 300 μm [11]. The epoxy resin, Epolam 2020, has a density of 1.10 g/cm³ for cured resin [20]. The mechanical properties of the different used materials are presented in Table 1. Composite plates were manufactured at Pprime Institute by contact moulding. A specific mould has been developed, enabling hemp yarns to be well-positioned, with a distance of 15mm between each yarn. The composite plates were cured with the following cycle: 24 h at ambient temperature, 3 h at 40°C, 2 h at 60°C, 2 h at 80°C and 4 h at 100°C. Glass transition temperature has been measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). It has been found to be equal to $89 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for the resin. Each specimen was cut into square samples, whose dimensions were about 10 x 10 mm² and whose thickness was equal to 2, 3 or 4 mm. In these samples, the single yarn was centred in x direction and positioned along z direction closer to the back face than to the front face (Fig. 3). Front faces were covered with aluminium painting and a sample holder was used for each shock (Fig. 1a).

	T _g (°C)	In-tension quasi-static modulus (MPa)		In-tension quasi-static strength (MPa)		Ref
		Longitudinal	Transverse	Longitudinal	Transverse	
Hemp yarn		23000±3000	1264±154	601±79	65±1	[21]
Epolam 2020	89±2	3100 ±200		69±5.5		[11]

Table 1: Characteristics of used materials.

Figure 3: Three-dimensional schematic representation of a single hemp yarn composite specimen.

4 DAMAGE ANALYSIS

4.1 Interfacial and resin damage

One laser shock test has been performed on each specimen. The laser intensity level was tuned by using different optical densities on the beam path. After the shocks, samples can be recovered from the experimental setup in spite of the important pressure apply. This is possible thanks to the shortness of

the pressure pulse. Observations were made with an optical microscope, using transmitted light. Two different types of damage were noticed, common to all the tested configurations (Fig. 4) One can be found at the interface between the yarn and the resin, and the other one in the resin.

Figure 4: Damage types observed in laser shocked single-yarn specimens.

The first type that appears is a micro-damage localised at the interface (see observations in Fig. 5). The shape of this interfacial micro-damage is quite unusual: it initiates at one interfacial point, probably a small defect at the interface, and propagates through the resin, towards the exterior of the yarn. The resulting cone shaped cracks, presented in Fig. 5b, remind interfacial cracks observed by Feillard et al. [22] during fragmentation test on glass/epoxy specimens (Fig. 6). Nevertheless, in case of laser shocks, the load is applied perpendicularly to the yarn/resin interface, which explains that the observed damage is 90°-turned in comparison with the one describes by Feillard et al.[22].

It has been observed that this interface damage appears above a given laser intensity value, which should correspond to the damage threshold of the interface. Its quantity and size increase with the laser intensity level. The smallest to be measured was about 20 µm wide. No privileged direction of these cracks has been noticed, which can be explained by the random positions and shapes of natural fibres in the yarn.

Figure 5: Interfacial damage observations in hemp yarn-Epolam 2020 samples; a) 0.31 GW/cm² and 4 mm thickness, b) 0.5 GW/cm² and 3 mm thickness, c) 0.21 GW/cm² and 2 mm thickness.

Figure 6: Sketches of the 3D micro-damage initiated by interfacial failure a) observed in fragmentation test [22], b) observed in laser shock test.

The second type of damage is large cracks in the resin, localised between the yarn and the specimen back face as shown in Fig. 7. These cracks are due to the boundary conditions induced by the sample holder (Fig. 1a), leading to a bending phenomenon in the specimen for high laser intensity level. As for interface damage, these resin cracks appear above a given level of the laser intensity, corresponding to resin damage threshold, and their dimensions increase with the laser intensity level.

Figure 7: Resin crack observation in hemp yarn-Epolam 2020 sample (0.57 GW/cm², 4 mm thickness).

4.2 Damage thresholds

Damage observations allow determining a range in which an interfacial damage threshold, in term of laser intensity level, is included. A range is defined between the highest laser intensity level for which no interface damage was found and the lowest level for which damage was observed. Data for single yarn with fully synthetic matrix are collected in Table 2. For specimens without water immersion, interfacial damage starts at 0.31 GW/cm², thus the threshold is found between 0.25 and 0.31 GW/cm². Tests before and after the threshold have been duplicated (at 0.24 and 0.25 GW/cm², and at 0.31 and 0.33 GW/cm²). The small variations in the intensity between duplicated shots are due to the laser source variation and do not deeply influence the pressure level induced inside the resin, thus validating the determined damage threshold range [23]. In this configuration, the resin damage is observed from a level of a laser intensity of 0.57 GW/cm² (Table 2). Table 2 also presents data concerning single yarn with Epolam samples which have been immersed in water for 28 days before testing. It can be observed that the water treatment has no significant influence on interface damage threshold. Indeed, the threshold is located between 0.25 and 0.31 GW/cm² for the dried specimens, when it is between 0.27 and 0.36 GW/cm² for the immersed specimens. A little porosity observed in the resin in the sample n°11 shocked at 0.36 GW/cm² explains that resin damage has been initiated for such a low laser energy level (Table 2). These preliminary results seem to demonstrate that interface adhesion in such material is not very sensitive to water sorption.

	Sample number	Thickness (mm)	Intensity (Gw/cm ²)	Interfacial damage	Resin damage
Single yarn sample with Epolam	01	3.73	0.05		
	02	3.77	0.09		
	03	3.84	0.16		
	04	3.53	0.24		
	05	3.83	0.25		
	06	3.71	0.31	X	
	07	3.69	0.33	X	
	08	3.81	0.40	X	
	09	3.53	0.57	X	X
Single yarn sample with Epolam, immersed 28 days in water at ambient temperature	10	3.81	0.27		
	11	3.57	0.36	X	X
	12	3.41	0.56	X	

Table 2: Threshold range for the two types of damage in single hemp yarn/Epolam tested specimens.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study deals with the possibility of using the laser shock test for studying the adhesion between fibre and matrix in composite materials.

For this first test campaign, specific specimens made of a single hemp yarn in an epoxy matrix have been tested. A set of samples has been immersed in water for 28 days before laser testing, in order to study the water sorption effect on interfacial adhesion quality.

Shocks have been performed by using the laser source available at PPRIME Institute. After being tested, samples were observed by optical microscopy, in transmitted light mode. For high laser intensity levels, two different types of damage have been observed: micro-damage at the yarn/matrix interface, and resin cracks located between the yarn and the sample back face. The interfacial micro-damage has an unusual cone shape, due to the laser loading characteristics. Several laser intensity levels have been applied, enabling the determination of damage thresholds of these two types of damage for each configuration of samples. Results show that resin cracks appear only for high laser intensity levels, in relation with the bending loading created by the sample holder. Interfacial damage appears earlier, and the reproducibility of the threshold value determination has been demonstrated. Moreover, by comparing threshold values of the interfacial damage in samples with or without water immersion, it has been shown that hemp/epoxy matrix interface is not very sensitive to water sorption.

These preliminary results demonstrate the ability of the laser shock test to study and quantify the mechanical quality of yarn/matrix interface. It opens the way for studying many types of fibre/matrix interfaces in different composite materials, with the objective of optimizing the interface adhesion quality.

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REFERENCES

- [1] O. Faruk, A. K. Bledzki, H.-P. Fink, and M. Sain, Biocomposites reinforced with natural fibers: 2000–2010, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **37**, 2012, pp.1552–1596.
- [2] P. S. Chua and M. R. Piggott, The glass fibre-polymer interface: II—Work of fracture and shear stresses, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **22**, 1985, pp.107–119.
- [3] E. Mäder, S. Gao, and R. Plonka, Static and dynamic properties of single and multi-fiber/epoxy composites modified by sizings, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **67**, 2007, pp.1105–1115.
- [4] B. Miller, P. Muri, and L. Rebenfeld, A microbond method for determination of the shear strength of a fiber/resin interface, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **28**, 1987, pp.17–32.

- [5] F. Vautard, P. Fioux, J. Schultz, M. Nardin, and B. Defoort, Using the thiol-ene reaction to improve adhesion strength in carbon fiber-acrylate composites cured by ultra violet light, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **286**, 2013, pp.12–21.
- [6] T.-T.-L. Doan, H. Brodowsky, and E. Mäder, Jute fibre/epoxy composites: Surface properties and interfacial adhesion, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **72**, 2012, pp.1160–1166.
- [7] T. H. D. Sydenstricker, S. Mochnaz, and S. C. Amico, Pull-out and other evaluations in sisal-reinforced polyester biocomposites, *Polym. Test.* **22**, 2003, pp.375–380.
- [8] J.-M. Park, S. T. Quang, B.-S. Hwang, and K. L. DeVries, Interfacial evaluation of modified Jute and Hemp fibers/polypropylene (PP)-maleic anhydride polypropylene copolymers (PP-MAPP) composites using micromechanical technique and nondestructive acoustic emission, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **66**, 2006, pp.2686–2699.
- [9] S. J. Eichhorn and R. J. Young, Composite micromechanics of hemp fibres and epoxy resin microdroplets, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **64**, 2004, pp.767–772.
- [10] F. G. Torres and M. L. Cubillas, Study of the interfacial properties of natural fibre reinforced polyethylene, *Polym. Test.* **24**, 2005, pp.694–698.
- [11] C. Guillebaud-Bonafous, D. Vasconcellos, F. Touchard, and L. Chocinski-Arnault, Experimental and numerical investigation of the interface between epoxy matrix and hemp yarn, *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **43**, 2012, pp.2046–2058.
- [12] J. T. Kim and A. N. Netravali, Development of aligned-hemp yarn-reinforced green composites with soy protein resin: Effect of pH on mechanical and interfacial properties, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **71**, 2011, pp.541–547.
- [13] J. Vossen, Adhesion measurement of thin films, thick film, and bulk coatings, 1978, pp.122–131.
- [14] J. Yuan and V. Gupta, Measurement of interface strength by the modified laser spallation technique. I. Experiment and simulation of the spallation process, *J. Appl. Phys.* **74**, 1993, pp.2388–2397.
- [15] M. Braccini and M. Dupeux, *Mechanics of solid interfaces*, Wiley, 2012.
- [16] R. Ecault, M. Boustie, F. Touchard, F. Pons, L. Berthe, L. Chocinski-Arnault, B. Ehrhart, and C. Bockenheimer, A study of composite material damage induced by laser shock waves, *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **53**, 2013, pp.54–64.
- [17] L. Ferrante, J. Tirillò, F. Sarasini, F. Touchard, R. Ecault, M. A. Vidal Urriza, L. Chocinski-Arnault, and D. Mellier, Behaviour of woven hybrid basalt-carbon/epoxy composites subjected to laser shock wave testing: Preliminary results, *Compos. Part B Eng.* **78**, 2015, pp.162–173.
- [18] A. Perrier, R. Ecault, F. Touchard, M. Vidal Urriza, J. Baillargeat, L. Chocinski-Arnault, and M. Boustie, Towards the development of laser shock test for mechanical characterisation of fibre/matrix interface in eco-composites, *Polym. Test.*
- [19] C. Bonnafous, Analyse multi échelle des mécanismes d'endommagement de composites chanvre/époxy à renforts tissés. Caractérisation de l'interface fibre/matrice., PhD Thesis, ENSMA, 2010.
- [20] D. S. de Vasconcellos, F. Touchard, and L. Chocinski-Arnault, Tension–tension fatigue behaviour of woven hemp fibre reinforced epoxy composite: A multi-instrumented damage analysis, *Int. J. Fatigue* **59**, 2014, pp.159–169.
- [21] D. Silva de Vasconcellos, Comportement en fatigue avant et après impact de composites tissés chanvre/époxy, PhD Thesis, ENSMA, 2013.
- [22] P. Feillard, G. Désarmot, and J. P. Favre, A critical assement of the fragmentation test for glass/epoxy systems, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **49**, 1993, pp.109–119.
- [23] R. Ecault, L. Berthe, M. Boustie, F. Touchard, E. Lescoute, A. Sollier, P. Mercier, and J. Benier, Observation of the shock wave propagation induced by a high-power laser irradiation into an epoxy material, *J. Phys. Appl. Phys.* **46**, 2013, pp.235501.